

Direct Observation of Huge Flexoelectric Polarization around Crack Tips

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S Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: Flexoelectricity is especially relevant for nanoscale structures, and it is expected to be largest at the tip of cracks. We demonstrate the presence of a huge flexoelectric polarization at crack tips in SrTiO₃ by direct observation with scanning transmission electron microscopy. We observe an averaged polarization of $62 \pm 16 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ in the three unit cells adjacent to the crack tip, which is one of the largest flexoelectric polarizations ever reported. The polarization is screened by an electron density of $0.7 \pm 0.1 \text{ e}^-/\text{uc}$ localized within one unit cell. These findings reveal the relevance of flexoelectricity for the science of crack formation and propagation.

KEYWORDS: Flexoelectricity, crack tips, transmission electron microscopy, strain gradient

Flexoelectricity, the electromechanical coupling between strain gradients and polarization, is especially relevant for nanoscale structures.^{1–5} The flexoelectric effect is weak in bulk materials, because strain gradients are typically small. In nanoscale structures, however, larger strain gradients are possible, and polarizations comparable to those of ferroelectric materials can be achieved.^{6–9} Examples include a huge flexoelectricity observed in bent-core nematic liquid crystals¹⁰ and rotation of polarization away from the ferroelectric polarization axis in twin domains in strained PbTiO₃ thin films.¹¹ Furthermore, flexoelectricity can be used to mechanically write polarization in ferroelectric thin films,^{12–14} to modulate electrical transport in two-dimensional electron systems,¹⁵ and to control tunneling barriers.¹⁶ Flexoelectricity also allows microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) such as cantilevers to be realized without using piezoelectric materials.^{17,18}

The largest strain gradients that materials can withstand occur around the tips of cracks. Therefore, flexoelectricity is relevant to the science of crack formation and propagation.¹⁹ Flexoelectricity affects cracks in all materials, because the flexoelectric effect is not limited to polar materials or even to crystalline materials.¹ In polar materials, however, it additionally induces a fracture asymmetry depending on whether the flexoelectric polarization induced by the strain gradients at the crack tip is aligned parallel or antiparallel to the uniform polarization in the material.²⁰ The electric fields generated by flexoelectricity at microfracture sites in bone have been suggested to induce osteocyte apoptosis and thus initiate crack-healing processes.²¹ A direct study of the polarization

around cracks at the nanoscale, however, has not yet been performed. A recent study investigated polarization around dislocations in SrTiO₃.²² The strain fields resulting from these dislocations indeed induce a flexoelectric polarization, and a polarization of $\sim 28 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ was found at distances smaller than 1 nm away from the dislocations. These dislocations, however, were formed at high temperatures, and therefore, ion diffusion can lead to composition variation and partial strain relief. Here, we show that cracks induced by a nonequilibrium epitaxial strain-relief process produce large strain gradients and large flexoelectric polarization.

We selected the SrMnO₃/SrTiO₃ epitaxial system for our study, because the flexoelectric effect in both materials is well studied.^{22–29} SrTiO₃ is a quantum paraelectric at low temperatures.³⁰ A large flexoelectric response is expected, because flexoelectric coefficients depend on the dielectric constant of the material. The flexoelectric coefficients of SrTiO₃ indeed scale with its dielectric constant and are therefore strongly temperature-dependent. The bulk coefficients are of the order 10^{-9} – 10^{-8} C m^{-1} at room temperature.²⁴ SrMnO₃ is a paraelectric material close to a ferroelectric transition. Ferroelectricity can be induced by cation substitution,³¹ large tensile strain,^{32,33} or small tensile strain together with structural defects.³⁴ Furthermore, the flexoelectric rotation of the polarization has been observed in

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Figure 1. (a, b) AFM images of the surface of a SrMnO₃ film showing the absence and presence of long cracks parallel to the [100] and [010] lattice directions at stage 1 and stage 2, respectively. (c) XRD θ - 2θ scan of the sample measured before and after the appearance of the cracks. The out-of-plane lattice parameter of the SrMnO₃ relaxes after the cracks appear. (d, e) RSMs of the 103 reflection before and after the appearance of the cracks. At stage 2, a tail of the intensity of the film peak is distributed at higher absolute values of Q_{in} indicating an in-plane strain relaxation.

Figure 2. Overview of the sample and close-up images of the cracks. (a) HAADF-STEM image of the SrTiO₃/SrMnO₃ heterostructure. The yellow dotted line marks the interface, the white arrows mark the shallow cracks, and the yellow arrow mark a deep crack. (b) HAADF image of a shallow crack. The SrMnO₃ lattice splits at a MnO₂ plane. (c) HAADF image of a deep crack. An edge dislocation appears at the crack tip. The box region is the reference for the corresponding strain analysis.

films with vertical strain gradients induced by a gradual distribution of oxygen vacancies.²⁸ By quantifying the strain gradient and the induced polarization, a longitudinal flexoelectric coefficient of SrMnO₃ of $4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ C m}^{-1}$ was found in the ferroelectric phase.²⁸

SrMnO₃ grows very well on SrTiO₃, resulting in a coherent epitaxy at the growth temperature, i.e. 800 °C. The SrMnO₃ layer is under biaxial tensile strain, which increases with decreasing temperature due to the difference in the thermal expansion coefficients of the materials. The strain in SrMnO₃ is 1.8% at the growth temperature and 2.0% at 300 K. Therefore, it is possible for such a thin film to have a thickness below the critical thickness for stress relief at high temperatures and above the critical thickness at room temperature. Furthermore, SrMnO₃ is expected to be oxygen-deficient at high temperatures and to incorporate oxygen during cooling.³⁵ Oxygen incorporation shrinks the lattice and thus increases the strain. During and after cooling, cracks appear in the film, because the temperature is too low to allow for stress relief by the creation of dislocations.^{36,37} Evidence for this mechanism was found by the observation of cracks in a SrMnO₃ layer, but not in a layer

capped by an epitaxial overgrown layer.³⁸ This process is the initial phase of stress relief mechanisms by delamination commonly observed in oxide films.^{39–41}

Results. We grew several SrMnO₃ film samples with thicknesses of 8–25 nm using pulsed laser deposition, as described in detail in the **Methods** section. The films were grown in the layer-by-layer growth mode as made evident by clear reflection high-energy electron diffraction (RHEED) intensity oscillations. Directly after growth (stage 1), we investigated the surface morphology of a SrMnO₃ film with a thickness of 8 nm with atomic force microscopy (AFM). We observed smooth terraces with single-unit-cell-high steps in **Figure 1a**. Some large single-unit-cell-high islands were present on the terraces. We did not observe cracks at this stage. However, when we reinvestigated the samples at a later stage (stage 2), cracks had appeared (**Figure 1b**). This time scale for crack formation depends on the thicknesses of the films and ranges from days to several weeks. A large number of cracks are visible in the SEM image of the film surface (see **Figure S1**). The cracks are straight and aligned with the [100] and [010] crystal lattice directions. The average separation of the cracks

in the SEM image is ~ 100 nm, and the cracks are continuous for lengths of 100–2000 nm.

In order to investigate whether the cracks are caused by strain relaxation, we performed X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements. Figure 1c shows a θ - 2θ scan of a SrMnO₃ film with a thickness of 8 nm. The sample was measured both at stage 1 and at stage 2. The XRD scan shows the SrTiO₃ 002 reflection and the SrMnO₃ 002 reflection. The latter peak is broad because of the finite thickness effect. Comparing the two measurements, the intensity of the film peak at stage 2 is reduced, and the maximum of the peak is shifted from $Q_{\text{out}} = 3.337 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ to $Q_{\text{out}} = 3.326 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. This indicates that the out-of-plane lattice parameter of the SrMnO₃ has changed from 3.766 to 3.778 Å, consistent with partial epitaxial stress relief. Figure 1d,e shows reciprocal space maps (RSMs) around the 103 reflection. Here, a decrease in intensity at stage 2 is observed as well, together with a shift of the film peak toward lower Q_{out} values. At stage 1, the peak position along Q_{in} is equal to $Q_{\text{in}} = 1.609 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, which corresponds to the Q_{in} value of the SrTiO₃ peak, indicating a coherently strained layer. At stage 2, in contrast, only part of the peak intensity is at $Q_{\text{in}} = 1.609 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, and a tail of the intensity is distributed at higher absolute values of Q_{in} . This implies that a part of the film is no longer coherently strained and that strain gradients are therefore present in the sample. Because XRD measurements probe a large area, the stress relief is found to affect most of the film.

To investigate the atomic structure of the sample in detail, we used atomic-column-resolved scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM). Experimental details including the TEM specimen preparation and STEM operation conditions are described in the Methods section. Figure 2a displays the overview of a SrMnO₃ thin film cross-section by high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF)-STEM imaging along the [100] direction. The yellow dotted line marks the heterointerface between SrMnO₃ and SrTiO₃, which is determined by the corresponding strain analysis (see also Figure S2). We observed several cracks, as highlighted by arrows. Most cracks terminate at the interface (white arrows), but some cracks also penetrate into the SrTiO₃ (yellow arrow).

In order to study the structure of the cracks in more detail, we acquired images at high magnification of the cracks with the HAADF detector. Figure 2b shows a close-up image of a shallow crack. The crack is centered around a MnO₂ (010) plane. At the apex of the crack, six Mn columns can be identified, which have progressively weaker intensity with increasing distance from the interface. These Mn columns are not displaced along y with respect to the underlying SrTiO₃ crystal. No crystalline material is found in the center of the crack at distances larger than six unit cells away from the interface. The Sr columns adjoining these Mn sites move outward with increasing distance from the interface, thereby increasing the Sr–Sr distance. This separation is approximately 1.5 unit cells at a distance of six unit cells away from the interface.

Some of the cracks are wider and penetrate further into the SrTiO₃ substrate. Figure 2c shows an example of such a crack. The atomic structure of the crack is more disordered compared to the shallow cracks. The crack is centered on the SrO plane. Whereas the Ti and Mn lattices split, and the corresponding atomic planes move apart, the Sr sublattice rearranges, and additional Sr columns are found directly at the interface and at the center of the crack. This edge dislocation in the Sr sublattice of the SrTiO₃ has a Burgers vector $a[010]$ and

terminates at a SrO plane in the SrTiO₃. Unlike previous work,⁴² we do not observe the diffusion of Mn ions into the tip of the deep crack (see also Figure S3). Because we only observe large strain gradients and induced flexoelectric polarization in the deep cracks, we focus on these cracks in the remainder of the Letter. We investigated a total of 4 deep cracks, all of which showed consistent results. A detailed analysis of the shallow cracks is presented in the Supporting Information.

To analyze the strain fields surrounding the cracks, we apply geometric phase analysis (GPA) to the STEM image in Figure 2c. Figure 3a,b is the corresponding out-of-plane strain (ϵ_{xx})

Figure 3. Geometric phase analysis of the deep crack. (a) Out-of-plane strain (ϵ_{xx}) map and (b) in-plane strain (ϵ_{yy}) map of the deep crack. The large in-plane strain is observed at the tip of the crack. (c, d) Calculated absolute values of strain gradients $d\epsilon_{xx}/dx$ and $d\epsilon_{yy}/dy$, respectively. An averaged strain gradient $d\epsilon_{yy}/dy$ of 0.21 nm^{-1} is present in an area of 3–4 unit cells around the tip of the crack.

and in-plane strain (ϵ_{yy}) maps of the deep crack, respectively. The ϵ_{xx} map indicates the position of the interface, showing a strain of 5% around the crack tip. The typical dislocation loop appears in the ϵ_{yy} map, indicating the dislocation core in the Sr sublattice of SrTiO₃. The strain is as high as 20%. The color changes in the ϵ_{yy} map around the crack tip reveal the inhomogeneous strain distribution. Figure 3c,d shows the calculated absolute values of strain gradients $d\epsilon_{xx}/dx$ and $d\epsilon_{yy}/dy$, respectively. We find that strong strain gradients appear in the $d\epsilon_{yy}/dy$ map and are confined to within three unit cells around the crack tip. The strain gradients at opposite sides of the crack are of similar magnitude but opposite in sign. The largest strain gradient is observed in the y direction, with a magnitude as high as 3.0 nm^{-1} . The strain gradients $d\epsilon_{xx}/dy$, $d\epsilon_{yy}/dx$, $d\epsilon_{xy}/dx$, and $d\epsilon_{xy}/dy$ are discussed in the Supporting Information (see also Figure S4).

With the quantification of large strain gradients, we now are able to describe the electrical polarization around the tip of the deep crack. Atomically resolved STEM enables a precise determination of the atomic-column positions, allowing the observation of lattice displacements at a few picometer precision.⁴³ Figure 4a shows the displacement vector (D) map between Ti and neighboring Sr columns for the deep crack. The error of D depends on the quality of the 2-dimensional Gaussian fitting of the atomic column positions.

Figure 4. Lattice displacement analysis around the deep crack. (a) Displacement vector map between the TiO and Sr columns overlaid with the HAADF image. The big yellow arrow highlights the interfacial SrO plane between SrMnO₃ and SrTiO₃. Polarization is observed in a region about 3–4 unit cells surrounding the crack tip (red arrows). (b, c) Schematic images for the relative displacement of TiO columns with respect to the four neighboring Sr columns at the upper side and the lower side of the crack tip. (d) Magnitude map of displacement vectors in the region defined by the red and yellow arrows in part a.

Figure 5. STEM-EELS investigation of the deep crack. (a) Colored HAADF image of the deep crack. White circles mark 9 TiO columns placed along the line through the maximum of the polarization field. (b) Ti-L_{2,3} spectra at the different positions marked in part a. The red and blue lines are the reference spectra for Ti⁴⁺ and Ti³⁺, respectively. The Ti column at the center of the crack has a reduced valence state of $+3.3 \pm 0.1$ (spectrum 5).

In this work, we realized a high-quality Gaussian fitting of atomic columns around the tip of the deep crack, yielding the determination of atomic displacement with high accuracy (see Figure S6). The directions of the displacement vectors are aligned at both sides of the crack tip, pointing to the crack tip. The aligned region is about 3–4 unit cells surrounding the crack tip, which correlates well with the location of the strain gradients. The relative position of Ti is shifted upward for the upper side (Figure 4b) and downward for the lower side (Figure 4c). Away from the tip region, the displacement vectors are randomly oriented, reflecting the measurement

uncertainty. Figure 4d maps the corresponding magnitude of the displacement vector in Figure 4a. It shows that the values close to the crack tip are larger than those in other regions.

For perovskite materials, quantitative mapping of electrical polarization can be performed using cation displacement in Z-contrast STEM images.⁴⁴ Since the ion charge centers are all collinear, the polarization (P) can be determined from the displacement between the position of the Ti atom and the centroid of the neighboring Sr columns mentioned above (Figure 4b,c). The polarization (P) is calculated using the formula $P = -2.5 D \mu C \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ pm}^{-1}$, where D is the

displacement.⁴⁵ Because of the linear relation between the cation displacement and the polarization, the electrical polarization increases upon approaching the crack tip. The tip of the deep crack acts as a 180° domain wall with a head-to-head configuration. The averaged magnitude of the spontaneous polarization for the upper side domain is $67 \pm 16 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$, and for the lower side it is $56 \pm 16 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$. The largest polarization in a single unit cell is $107 \pm 16 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$. Here, the noise levels were estimated from the apparent behavior of the nonpolar SrTiO₃ substrate.

The observed polarization is expected to be accompanied by electric charges accumulating at the tip of the crack. To study the charge states at the crack tip, we carried out electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS) measurements. As indicated in Figure 5a, we extracted Ti-L_{2,3} spectra from nine TiO columns around the crack tip. The Ti-L_{2,3} white lines shift to lower energy, and the splitting between the t_{2g} and e_g peaks becomes less pronounced, when approaching the crack tip (Figure 5b). This indicates a valence change of Ti within one unit cell around the crack tip. The valence state of Ti at the crack tip is $+3.3 \pm 0.1$, as determined by fitting reference Ti-L_{2,3} spectra for Ti⁴⁺ (SrTiO₃, red curve) and for Ti³⁺ (LaTiO₃, blue curve) at the bottom of Figure 5b to the Ti-L_{2,3} spectrum at the crack tip (spectrum 5).⁴⁶ The valence state of Ti in the unit cells adjacent to the crack tip is close to +4.0.

Discussion. We observe a high polarization at the cracks that penetrate into the SrTiO₃. We attribute the polarization to the flexoelectric effect, because (i) the polarization is exclusively observed in regions where the strain gradient $d\epsilon_{yy}/dy$ is large, and (ii) the sign of the polarization matches the sign of the strain gradient. The average polarization of $62 \pm 16 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ is the largest flexoelectric polarization observed so far. Together with the polarization, we also observed a valence state change of -0.7 ± 0.1 of the Ti ions at the tip of the crack. This valence change is much larger than previously observed polarization-induced valence changes.²² By analyzing the crack tip as a head-to-head domain wall, the charge density required to screen the average polarization of $62 \pm 16 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ is $0.6 \pm 0.15 \text{ e}^-/\text{uc}$, which is in good agreement with the measured charge density. Although we cannot directly rule out composition changes such as O vacancies (see Figure S8) or Sr interstitials as the cause of the charge density, we attribute the charge density to the flexoelectric polarization, because both its magnitude and its location match the screening charge expected from the flexoelectric polarization. The main reason that the polarization is so large, is that the strain gradients at the crack tips are 5–1000 times larger than previously investigated nanoscale strain gradients.^{6,11,16,22} The longitudinal flexoelectric coefficient μ_{11} is given by $\mu_{11} = P_y/(d\epsilon_{yy}/dy)$.¹ The average of the strain gradient in the boxed areas in Figure 4a is 0.21 nm^{-1} . Therefore, we observe the longitudinal flexoelectric coefficient μ_{11} of SrTiO₃ at the crack tip to be $3 \times 10^{-9} \text{ C m}^{-1}$, in good agreement with bulk measurements.²⁴

To estimate the importance of the flexoelectric polarization in crack formation and crack propagation processes, we compare the elastic energy density with the electrostatic and flexoelectric energy densities at the crack tip. The former is given by $E_{\text{elas}}/V = 0.5Y \cdot \epsilon^2$, where E_{elas} is the elastic energy, V is the volume, and Y is Young's modulus. Using the average strain and $Y = 270 \text{ GPa}$,⁴⁷ we find $E_{\text{elas}}/V = 2.3 \times 10^9 \text{ Jm}^{-3}$. The electrostatic energy density is given by $E_{\text{elec}}/V = 0.5\chi^{-1} \cdot P^2$, where E_{elec} is the electrostatic energy, and χ is the dielectric susceptibility. Using the average polarization of the boxes in

Figure 4a, and $\chi_{\text{STO}} = 300\epsilon_0$, we find $E_{\text{elec}}/V = 7.2 \times 10^7 \text{ Jm}^{-3}$. Here, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum. The flexoelectric energy density is given by $E_{\text{flex}}/V = 0.5 \mu \cdot \chi^{-1} \cdot P \cdot d\epsilon_{yy}/dy$, where E_{flex} is the flexoelectric energy. Using $\mu = 3 \times 10^{-9} \text{ C m}^{-1}$, we find $E_{\text{flex}}/V = 7.4 \times 10^7 \text{ Jm}^{-3}$. Therefore, the flexoelectric and electrostatic energies provide significant contributions to the energy of the crack.

Conclusions. In summary, we have demonstrated the presence of large flexoelectric polarization at crack tips in SrTiO₃. We created cracks in SrTiO₃ by exploiting a thermal-strain relaxation process in SrMnO₃ thin films. The averaged polarization of $62 \pm 16 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ is the largest flexoelectric polarization measured so far. The polarization is screened by an electron density of $0.7 \pm 0.1 \text{ e}^-/\text{uc}$ localized within one unit cell. Both the flexoelectric and electrostatic energy densities were found to be ~3% of the elastic energy. This finding implies that flexoelectricity may influence the processes of crack formation and propagation. Furthermore, we observe unusual electronic and chemical states present at crack tips due to large local electronic reconstructions induced by flexoelectric effects.

Methods. We prepared the SrTiO₃ substrates (Shinkosha, (001) orientation) by sonification in water and then either by a combination of etching with a buffered HF solution and *ex situ* annealing at 1050 °C or by *in situ* annealing at 1400 °C. Both procedures result in a singly terminated TiO₂ surface.^{48,49} The SrMnO₃ films were grown by pulsed laser deposition using a stoichiometric, polycrystalline target (Lesker). The growth temperature was 800 °C, the oxygen pressure 0.05 mbar, the laser fluence 2 J cm^{-2} , the laser frequency 1 Hz, and the growth rate 0.04 monolayer per pulse. The growth mode is a layer-by-layer growth as made evident by the observation of reflection high-energy electron diffraction (RHEED) oscillations. The surface morphology of the samples was investigated with atomic force microscopy (AFM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The XRD measurements were performed with a Panalytical Empyrean diffractometer in high-resolution mode. We define the out-of-plane component of the momentum transfer Q_{out} as the component of Q parallel to the [001] direction of the SrTiO₃ crystal and the in-plane component Q_{in} as the component parallel to the [100] direction.

TEM specimens in cross-sectional orientation were prepared by tripod polishing followed by argon ion milling at liquid nitrogen temperature using a precision ion polishing system (PIPS, Gatan, model 691). TEM investigations were carried out by using a spherical aberration-corrected microscope (JEOL ARM200F, JEOL Co. Ltd.) with a DCOR probe corrector (CEOS GmbH) at 200 kV. The microscope is equipped with a cold-field emission gun (CFEG) and Gatan GIF Quantum ERS energy filter with dual-EELS acquisition capability. The STEM images were obtained with a convergent semiangle of 20.4 mrad. The corresponding inner and outer collection semiangles for HAADF imaging were 70–300 mrad. The corresponding probe current was 14 pA, and the magnitude of electron dose was in the order of $10^3 \text{ e}^- \text{ \AA}^{-2}$. To improve the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and to minimize the drift and the image distortion of high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) images, 10 serial frames were acquired with short dwell time ($2 \mu\text{s pixel}^{-1}$). The image series were then aligned and superimposed. To minimize the sample tilt effects,⁵⁰ we optimized the alignment of the sample to the [100] zone axis using PACBED (see Figure S5). Dual EELS

spectrum imaging was performed with a collection semiangle of 111 mrad. The corresponding probe current was 80 pA, and the magnitude of electron dose was in the order of $10^6 \text{ e}^- \text{ \AA}^{-2}$. All EELS spectra were acquired with a dispersion of 0.1 eV channel⁻¹ at an energy resolution of 0.7 eV. An online script⁵¹ that can obtain multiframe spectrum images (SI) and perform an automatic energy-offset correction was used to acquire EELS spectra. The EELS spectra analysis was performed using a multiple linear least-squares fitting algorithm.

Strain states were obtained using Geometry Phase Analysis (GPA) developed by Martin Hÿtch.⁵² The displacement and polarization vector maps are obtained by quantitative analysis of the HAADF image using a DigitalMicrograph software tool⁵³ (see Figures S6 and S11). We crosschecked the results of the atomic displacement measurements by changing the scanning direction (see Figure S7), yielding identical results.

All AFM, XRD, and STEM measurements were performed at room temperature.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.nanolett.9b03176>.

SEM image of the SMO surface, strain analysis of the deep crack, and detailed studies of the shallow crack (PDF)

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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